

A Survey of CBIR System

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15524633>

Abstract

Content based image retrieval is one of the most important field of object recognition. It can be used to identify the object based upon its color, pattern, shape properties of an image. In earlier days they are based upon these properties the images are classified. But now a days deep learning based techniques are used focus on various image retrieval methods. This study can help the researcher to understand the idea in this field.

Keywords: *CBIR, CNN.*

Introduction

Image retrieval System is a computer system for browsing, identifying and retrieving similar images from a large database of digital images. Object recognition is most wanted area in the field of pattern recognition, image retrieval and artificial intelligence. Usually we can divide image retrieval by three categories that is Text-based image processing, Content-based retrieval and Semantic-based. The text-based approach can be traced back to 1970s. Since the images need to be manually annotated by text descriptors, it requires much human labour for annotation, and the annotation accuracy is subject to human perception.

Content-Based Image Retrieval (CBIR) is a technique for retrieving images on the basis of automatically-derived features such as colour, texture and shape. Image queries are characterized into three levels of abstraction: Primitive features such as colour or shape, logical features such as the identity of objects and abstract attributes such as the significance of the scenes depicted. CBIR systems currently operate effectively only at the lowest of these levels.

CBIR operates on a totally different principle from keyword indexing. Primitive features characterize the image content, such as colour, texture and shape are computed for both stored and query images, and these features are used to identify the stored images most closely matching the query. There are several commercial CBIR systems are now available IBM's QBIC, Virage's VIR Image Engine. In addition, demonstration versions of numerous experimental systems can be viewed on the Web, including MIT's Photobook and Columbia University's WebSEEK. CBIR systems are beginning to find a foothold in the marketplace, prime application areas include crime prevention (fingerprint and face recognition), intellectual property (trademark registration), journalism and advertising (video asset management) and Web searching. Both the AltaVista and Yahoo Search engines now have CBIR facilities.

An object recognition system is a computer system for searching and identifying images from a huge amount of digital images. Image recognition has been an important trending research area since the last few years, Basically, these systems helps to retrieve images similar to a user-defined specification or pattern. Their goal is to support image retrieval based on content properties (e.g., shape, color, texture), usually encoded into feature vector.

Deep Learning based Image Retrieval

It can be in supervision type, Network type or descriptor type. In supervision type it can be done by supervised, unsupervised, semi supervised, weakly supervised, pseudo supervised or self supervised method. In Network based use the convolutional network, Autoencoder, Siamese & Triplet, Generative Adversarial Attention or Reinforcement learning method. Some method use binary descriptor value or Real descriptor values are used for retrieval. In this paper presents various image retrieval methods James K.Shuttleworth et al. [1] have proposed the concept of classification of colon cancer images using co- occurrence matrix, here first the color value of an image is extracted then they are rotated at 3600 in each stage. The co- occurrence matrix is calculated for 0o,90o,180o,270o. Then all the values are normalized. From this normalized value, features are extracted. Then the distance formula is applied for similarity measurement.

Eva Horster et al. [2] have proposed the concept of image retrieval on large scale database which forms a co- occurrence matrix by vector quantization. From that gradient based feature, vectors are formed by using K-means clustering. Then the similarity is computed by cosine similarity.

Greg pass et al. [3] have proposed the concept of comparing images using color coherence. Here the image pixels are replaced by the average value in a small local neighbourhood, then the pixels are classified whether they are coherent or incoherent, then the pixel groups are determined by computing connected components of pairs. This pairs are compared by using their difference value between them.

Horst Eiden berger et al. [4] have used the semantic feature layer for image retrieval which forms the higher level features based upon the descriptors of the lower level features and It uses distance measurement for similarity calculation.

M. Ferreira et al. [5] use a 2D Walking and histogram for specifying shape descriptor. It resamples the image pixel dimension, then bilateral filter is applied for removing the iterative detail from an image for identifying edges by canny edge detectors, and from this scale map value, sub segments are formed, then noisy edge removal and decomposition process are applied. After the segmentation process, the highest relevance values are selected for the extraction of histogram. Then the indexing process is applied for image retrieval.

Yinig Deng et al. [6] have used the color values for image retrieval. For that color pixel, the values are calculated in each segmented region of an image. Colors are represented in CIELUV color space. After calculating the clusters, the distance between the clusters is computed.

Then the lattice structure is computed in the 3D color space and the indexing techniques are applied for storing data and form a voronoi cell or hierarchical lattice structure. Depending upon the distance, images are retrieved.

Anil K.Jain [7] has proposed the concept of Gabor filters for segmentation. Its filter selection is based on reconstruction of input image from the filtered image. It can act as blob detectors, then the texture feature are captured and the clustering is applied for segmentation

Poulami Haldar [8] has proposed the concept of image retrieval using histogram and color and edge. Then the distance is used to measure similarity.

Stathis et al. [9] have proposed the concept of texture classification based on multi-resolution histogram. It forms an image pyramid, then, it computes the histogram of an image. Then the values are smoothed and normalized and the cumulative histogram is computed. The differences between each level are calculated, then, it uses the distance formula for similarity measurement.

Koji Nakanaet al.[10] have proposed the concept of image retrieval using FPGA. It uses Verilog HDL source to identify the similarity.

Julians to ttinger[11]has proposed the concept of image retrieval by using interest point. They extract the intensity or color based interest point features of an image. So the local descriptor values

are computed, then the cluster using k-means algorithm is formed and the clusters are compared for similarity measurement.

B.S.Manjunath et al. [12] have proposed the concept of texture features for browsing and retrieval of image data which uses the Gabor wavelet transform and fourier transform for extracting the feature of an image. Then the distance formula is applied for similarity measurement.

G.H.Liua et al. [13] have proposed the concept of multi texton co-occurrence matrix for image retrieval which uses histogram and co-occurrence matrix for feature extraction and also it forms a feature vector for 0o, 45o, 90o and 135o, then it computes the distance for similarity measurement.

W.Niblack et al. [14] have proposed the concept of the qbic project. They have described the images by their colors, textures and shape features. Then the similarity is measured using Euclidean distance measurement.

J. Bach et al. [15] have proposed the concept of the virage image search engine which uses the global and local Color value, texture and shape features for retrieving similar images.

Alex pmentlant et al. [16] have proposed the concept of photobook which uses the normalized image value for its position, scale and orientation. It computes the texture and shape features, and then uses the stain energy for matching the similar images.

J.R. Smith [17] has proposed the concept of integrated spatial and feature image systems which describes text and color base image and video retrieval. Here it uses color histogram for matching.

Jitendra malik et al. [18] have proposed the concept of textons, contours and region of an image.

David A.Clausi [19] has proposed the concept of an analysis of gray level co- occurrence matrix and its image features.

Abdolreza Rashno and Elyas Rashno [20] have proposed the concept of image retrieval based upon the wavelet and color features and the wavelet feature and color feature are extracted from an image. After that, the adaptation and cooperation process are followed, then its value is indexed by ACO whose working principal is like an ant which tries to find the shortest path for finding a single solution. ACO is based on finding minimum cost method in the graph and they have traversed through this path until the final nodes are reached for finding the heuristic feature value, then the similarity is measured based upon the value retrieved.

Ashraf et al. [21] have proposed the concept of image retrieval based on color and discrete wavelet transform for extracting the color, texture and shape feature. After that, the distance is found for similarity measurement.

Figure 1 Performance Comparison between Various Methods

M. Ahmed et al. [22] have proposed the concept of image retrieval and they have used color moments for extracting the color feature, and they have also used discrete wavelet transform and Gabor wavelet method for extracting the texture features. Based upon the distance value similarity is measured.

Srinivas et al. [23] have proposed image retrieval using dictionary learning. They have used clustering for grouping similar images using dictionary. The orthogonal matching pursuit algorithm is used for matching similar images.

Texton co-occurrence matrix is used for the textures. The co-occurrence matrix is calculated for dimensions 00, 450, 900, 1350. In the method we also take all nearby pixels for compute the co-occurrence matrix. So that the accuracy of an image features will be increased, from that co-occurrence matrix the image features are retrieved. Based on the Euclidean distance measurement the images are classified.

Conclusion

This paper represent various methods for image retrieval. Each of them have their own implementation methods, and also it have both advantages and disadvantages. So researcher can use this for identifying better methods for their problems.

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